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THE ORIGIN OF NEOLOGISMS AND THEIR USAGE

Annotation: This article investigates the origin of neologisms and their usage. Furthermore, there are given a lot of neologisms with their translations and meanings.

Key words: neologisms, novelty, lexical neologisms, semantic neologisms, bishfteks, gamburger, yogurt, keks, ketchup, jem, kokteyl, koka-kola, pepsi-kola, pom, viski,

No matter what nation in the world, its place and position in the world civilization is determined by its unique national identity and historical experience. The first sign of national identity is the national language, which is one of the important conditions for the formation of a nation as a nation. Without language, there is no nation. The language is the means by which the nation is raised, the nation is raised to the level of a nation, and its existence and activity are determined. The cultural and spiritual wealth of the people, their intellect and thinking, scientific, historical and cultural riches are reflected in its language. In this sense, language is the heart and existence of the people. Language is the great and priceless spiritual wealth of the people, an inexhaustible treasure. So, language has been formed and existed for centuries.

The world we live in today is developing day by day. We can see these changes in every area such as politics, education, health, business, etc. such changes will also affect the words used by representatives of every developing industry in the country, and as a result of the changes, new words will be used in every field.

Vocabulary is the most dynamic, ever-evolving component. Innovations, developments and changes in society are reflected in the lexicon. Vocabulary development goes in two directions. On the one hand, the vocabulary is enriched by the expression of historical changes and innovations in the study of society in the process of its development. Vocabulary is enriched by words adopted in other languages, new words created, new terms, new phrases due to changes in the meaning of words. Vocabulary changes do not depend on the language system. On the other hand, the lexicon is enriched by creating new words using existing word tools.

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Languages are not protected from each other. One language can learn sounds, words and combinations from another language.

Assimilation, that is, the further increase of vocabulary by the learner, is enriched by the assimilation of neologisms to a more perfect, resonant, that is, to the rules of the acquired language.

Neologisms (Greek *neos* – new, *logos* – word) are words that describe the development of society, new things and concepts that have emerged in response to the demands of life. The novelty of neologisms is felt only when they first appear: over time, they lose their “novelty” and usually become active words.

So, neologisms are a new relationship in everyday life, a new one representing things and their signs, new phenomena, concepts can be recognized as lexical units. To the nature of such words neologisms are divided into two types according to some researchers:

1. Lexical neologisms.
2. Semantic neologisms.

As some researchers suggested lexical neologisms of the Uzbek language, which are not completely assimilated while they are borrowed from other languages and they are not used broadly. For example, *kollej*, *menejment*, *bakalavriyat*, *magistratura*, etc.

Semantic neologisms already exist in the language and are now new words used in the sense. For example, *noyib* (deputat), *tuman* (rayon), *viloyat* (oblast), *do'kon* (magazin), *tadbirkor*, *sarmoya*, *vazir*, *hokim*, *anjuman* (konferensiya) and etc.

Neologisms are considered to belong to different periods. For example, once upon a time terms such as “*avtobus*”, “*trolleybus*”, “*metro*” became a lexicon of modern layer that has lost its novelty today.

As a result of giving Uzbek language the status of the state language accelerated the process of penetrating neologisms, and hundreds and thousands of neologisms are appeared in our language. However, the process of penetrating neologisms from the other languages leads to losing the peculiarities of the Uzbek language. That is why, there should also be another process, which sorts out using borrowings in all the spheres of the society, changing them with the lexical units of the Uzbek language. If there is no such a chance, adopting of neologisms can occur.

English words in our language can be divided into thematic groups in the field of socio-political, economic, cultural- educational and sports. English assimilations of the thematic group of sports have become so widespread since independence that it is convenient and appropriate to study them systematically, separating them from the words of the cultural-educational sphere.

Today, many of the borrowed words mentioned in our dictionaries are used in the press. In particular, many lexemes used in the field of information technology do not have the recommended variants in Uzbek dictionaries. If necessary, they should be translated into Uzbek in accordance with the nature of our language and included in our dictionaries.

Below we consider the words of the thematic group on socio-political, economic, cultural-educational and sports on the basis of internal divisions:

Food name: *bishfteks*, *gamburger*, *yogurt*, *keks*, *ketchup*, *jem*, etc.

Drink names: *kokteyl*, *koka-kola*, *pepsi-kola*, *pom*, *viski*, etc.

Clothing names: *jemper*, *jinsi*, *pidjak*, *pajama*, *sviter*, *trusi*, *reglan*, etc.

The name of the household items: mikser, pleyer, etc.

Cosmetics and household themes: sheyping, shampun, fen, servis, etc.

Names denoting the concept of place: vokzal, kemping, klub, kollej, kottej, motel, tunnel, zoopark, xoll park, supermarket, etc.

Assimilated words related to the economics and trade: lizing, eksport, banknot, broker, varrant, vaucher, grant, diler, import, importyor, investor, barter, budjet, marketing, menejer, xolding, konsalting, biznesmen, biznes, etc.

Words related to the sport: aut, badminton, basketbol, vaterpolo, karting, match, motobol, lider, motocross, nokaut, nokdaun, raund, raund, record, ring, sport, start, futbol, finish, etc.

Among the English assimilation lexemes, those in the field of household and trade are also peculiar, and it can be said that the supermarket lexeme has now lost its neologistic character and moved to the modern layer. There are do'kon, minimarket, supermarket, gipermarket, megamarket, savdo majmuasi lexemes that enter the mall, and the gipermarket lexeme has a neologism character.

English assimilation lexemes, mainly nouns, sometimes have lexical-semantic relationships within other categories. The xuligan lexeme, which represents the character trait of human beings, enters into a semantic relationship with the lexemes of the adjective in the category of bezori, bevosh, and the sentimental lexeme enters into a semantic relationship with the ko'ngli bo'sh, ko'ngilchan, yig'loqi.

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